

Trend Analysis of Seasonal Rainfall and Temperature pattern in Afzalpur Taluk, Karnataka, India

^{1*}Channamma S. Gour, ¹Prakash Kariyajjanavar, ²K.Channabasappa, ³Arun Kumar. S.L.

¹Department of Environmental Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi 585106, Karnataka

¹Department of Environmental Science, Gulbarga University, Kalaburagi 585106, Karnataka

²Department of Geology, Central University of Karnataka, Kadaganchi, Kalaburagi

³Department of Civil Engineering, GM Institute of Technology Davangere-577 006, Karnataka

(*Corresponding author : Channamma S. Gour)

ABSTRACT:

The present study, which focused on climate variability, especially with regard to annual air temperature and rainfall, has received a great deal of attention global. The present study observes both long-term and short-term fluctuations in monsoon rainfall and temperature in the study area. Both rainfall and temperature data collected for the period of 2015 to 2019 were examined using, statistical trend analysis techniques was applied such as Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope estimator test were used to observe and analyze the problems. Statistically significant trends are noticed for rainfall, and the result is statistically significant at 95 % confident level during the period of 2015 to 2019. Rainfall is showing a quite good increasing trend (Sen's slope = 2.013) during monsoon season. In the case of maximum the temperature for the observed period, it showed a slight warming or increasing trend (Sen's slope = 0.21) while the minimum temperature trend showed a cooling trend (Sen's slope = -0.005), but the result of the maximum temperature trend analysis is statistically significant at 95 % confident level, on the different, the trend analysis result of minimum temperature is not statistically significant.

Key words: Rainfall. Temperature, Mann Kendall. Sen's slope. Trend analysis

INTRODUCTION:

Climate is one of the key components of the Earth's system. There are many variables such as temperature, rainfall, atmospheric pressure, and humidity that make up the weather, and understanding these variables is an essential task in studies on climate change detection. The understanding of past and latest climate change has garnered significant attention due to improvements and developments of various datasets and more advanced data analyses

worldwide. (Kumar *et al.*, 2010). Global climate changes may affect long-term rainfall patterns, impacting water availability, along with the risk of increasing occurrences of droughts and floods. (Pal and Mishra, 2017). The rainfall and temperatures (Singh *et al.*, 2013) are the most important fundamental physical parameters of the climate, as these parameters determine the environmental conditions of a particular region, which in turn affects agricultural productivity. (Modarres and da Silva, 2007, Kumar and Gautam, 2014). Agriculture and other related sectors, as well as food security and energy security in any region, are critically dependent on the timely availability of an adequate amount of water and a favorable climate. The rainfall received in an area is a crucial factor in determining the amount of water available to meet various demands such as agricultural, industrial, domestic water supply, and hydroelectric power generation. The pattern and amount of rainfall (Gajbhiye *et al.*, 2016) are among the most crucial factors influencing agricultural production, and agriculture plays a dominant role in India's economy and the livelihoods of its people. (Kumar and Gautam, 2014). In India, despite recent progress in industrialization, the strength of the economy is significantly reliant on the gross production of agricultural commodities, and agriculture is the backbone of millions of the densely populated areas, with crops predominantly dependent on natural rainfall. The southwest monsoon brings about 80% of the total precipitation in the country. Changes in the pattern, frequency, and variability of the Southwest monsoon (Sinha and Srivastava, 2000; Seo and Ummenhofer, 2017) would have a significant impact on agricultural production, water resource management, and the overall economy of the country. (Saha and Mooley, 1979). In light of the above, several studies have sought to examine the trend of climatic variables for the country. These studies have examined trends at the national level (Kumar *et al.*, 2010; Athar, 2015; Fan and Chen, 2016; Szabó *et al.*, 2019), regional levels (Bhutyani *et al.*, 2007; Elnesr *et al.*, 2010; Karpouzou and Kavalierataou, 2010; Duhan and Pandey, 2013; Duan *et al.*, 2017), and at individual stations. (Sahu *et al.*, 2012, 2013, 2014, 2016; Beyene, 2015, Arpita and Netrananda 2018). In fact, analysis at the local and regional scale (Fischer and Ceppi, 2012; Babar and Ramesh, 2013) is more relevant for creating specific development and adaptation plans to mitigate the negative effects of climate change. This article provides comprehensive coverage of the reported studies concerning two variables that are crucial in climate studies: rainfall and temperature. Temperature and its changes (Smadi, 2006; Tabari and Talaei, 2011) affect several hydrological processes, including rainfall, and these processes, in turn, also influence temperature. The trend

analysis of rainfall (Partal and Kahya, 2006; Addisu *et al.*, 2015; Neil and Notodiputro, 2016; Singh and Srivastava, 2016), temperature (Arora *et al.*, 2005; Karanurun and Kara, 2011; Meshram *et al.*, 2018), and other climatic variables across different spatial scales will aid in the development of future climate scenarios.

STUDY AREA:

Afzalpur Taluk situated in the northern part of Karnataka and western part of Kalaburagi. The research area covers 1050 sq.km. N-Latitudes $17^{\circ} 03' 30''$ – $17^{\circ} 22' 40''$ and E-Longitudes $76^{\circ} 12' 45''$ – $76^{\circ} 42' 35''$ (Fig.1).The whole southern boundary of the area is on the banks of River Bhima. Topographically the study area is very gentle slope (3 to 5%) towards southern direction. The entire study area comprises Deccan traps. This area has an arid and semi-arid climate. During the summer, the temperature fluctuates from 30 to 45 °C, during winter 28 to 31 °C monsoon occurs during June to August annual rainfall approximately 677 mm (CGWB 2011).

Figure 1: Shows location map of the study area

METHODOLOGY:

Rainfall, maximum and minimum temperature monthly average observed station data have analyzed for the study area of Afzalpur taluk from 2015 to 2019 (05 years), have been collected from District statistical office Kalaburagi. There are 4 rain gauge stations are located within the study area namely, Afzalpur, Atanoor, Gobbur and Karajagi. The rainfall data, that is from 2015 to 2019 of all the rain gauge stations are tabulated in the table (1). Trend is defined as the general movement of a series over an extended period of time or it is the long-term change in the dependent variable over a long period of time (Webber and Hawkins, 1980). Trend is determined by the relationship between the two variables of temperature, rainfall and their temporal resolution. The statistical method such as regression analysis and coefficient of determination R² are used for the significance of trend of temperature and rainfall. The trend were derived and tested by Mann–Kendall (M–K) trend test and slope of the regression line using the least squares method. The mean, SD and coefficient of variation (CV) of rainfall and temperatures have been calculated to analyze the relationship.

Mann Kendal Test

The M–K test is a statistical nonparametric test widely used for trend analysis in climatological and hydrological time series data. The test was suggested by Mann (1945) and has been extensively used with environmental time series. There are two advantages to use this test. First, it is a nonparametric test and does not require the data to be normally distributed. Second, the test has low sensitivity to abrupt breaks due to inhomogeneous time series. According to this test, the null hypothesis H₀ assumes that there is no trend (the data is independent and randomly ordered). This is tested against the alternative hypothesis H₁, which assumes that there is trend. The M–K statistic is computed as follows.

$$S = \sum_{k=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=k+1}^n \text{sgn}(x_j - x_k)$$

The trend test is applied to a time series X_k , which is ranked from $k = 1, 2, 3 \dots n-1$, which is ranked from $j = i + 1, i + 2, i + 3 \dots n$. Each of the data point's x_j is taken as a reference point,

$$\text{sgn}(x_j - x_k) = 1 \text{ if } x_j - x_k > 0$$

$$=0 \text{ if } x_j - x_k = 0$$

$$= -1 \text{ if } x_j - x_k < 0$$

This particular test has been calculated using XLSTAT 2017 software. A very high positive value of S is an indicator of an increasing trend and a very low negative value indicates a decreasing trend. The presence of a statistically significant trend is evaluated using Z value.

Sen's slope estimator test

The magnitude of a trend in a time series can be determined using a nonparametric method known as Sen's estimator (Sen, 1968). To estimate the true slope of an existing trend such as amount of change per year, Sen's nonparametric method is used and the test has been performed using XLSTAT 2017 software. A positive value of Sen's slope indicates an upward or increasing trend and a negative value gives a downward or decreasing trend in the time series.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Figure 2: Shows box and whisker plot of monthly rainfall in rain gauge stations in the study area

Table 1: Shows rainfall data (mm) of all rain gauge stations for the year 2015-2019 of the study area

Month	Rain gauge stations of the study area																			
	Afzalpur					Atanoor					Karajagi					Gobbur				
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Jan	1.1	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Feb	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
Mar	9.3	5.6	4.5	0.0	10.5	36.6	7.0	21.2	0.0	20.2	4.6	22.0	17.2	0.0	3.4	6.4	4.6	0.0	0.0	0.0
April	41.1	8.6	6.2	59.0	18.2	120.2	43.2	2.0	48.4	15.5	59.5	8.4	0.0	22	73.4	91.1	15.2	2.5	15.3	7.4
May	36.0	56.1	41.6	56.3	2.4	14.8	42.8	56.0	56.4	30.2	65.4	2.4	28	31.6	9.8	7.20	4.2	28.2	8.7	0.0
June	33.6	201.5	243.5	95.0	193.1	20.4	126.4	282.4	105.2	83.2	44.1	180.5	241.7	74.7	108.6	6.80	137.9	273.1	38.3	65.3
July	4.1	132.3	42.7	89.8	90.0	7.0	176.6	28.6	89.4	33.2	18.5	223.5	24.6	65.3	84.4	14.90	261.6	7.2	24.6	55.7
Aug	80.7	39.1	120.2	58.4	45.0	15.2	54.6	108.2	66.8	42.9	123.2	30.9	135.8	76.3	96.2	61.40	2.0	132.9	77.8	66.1
Sept	101.8	196.5	180.6	75.9	189.7	83.4	210.6	188.3	72.8	122.0	130.8	239.7	119.3	127.8	151.8	137.90	217.8	155.5	23.1	217.5
Oct	39.9	55.2	145.2	34.6	176.7	1.8	23.8	83.0	42.0	129.6	86.6	40.4	151	77.8	191.7	4.20	16.4	123	8.2	96.2
Nov	2.7	0.0	0.0	12.3	4.7	5.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	12.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	28.4	15	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	5.4
Dec	0.8	0.5	0.0	0.5	2.0	43.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	7.2	2.8	30.20	0.0	0.0	5.0	0.0
Total	351.1	695.4	784.5	481.8	732.3	347.4	685	769.7	481	489.2	532.7	747.8	717.6	511.1	737.1	360.1	659.7	722.4	201	513.6
Avg.	29.26	57.95	65.38	40.15	61.02	28.95	57.08	64.14	40.08	40.76	44.39	62.32	59.8	42.59	61.42	30.01	54.98	60.2	16.75	42.8
SD	33.60	76.92	85.16	36.82	80.00	37.55	73.68	89.87	39.11	46.03	48.86	93.68	81.28	40.15	66.34	44.28	94.95	89.91	22.75	64.94
CV%	114.85	131.88	130.26	91.71	131.02	129.57	129.08	140.11	97.58	112.93	110.07	150.33	135.92	96.61	108.00	147.57	172.71	149.35	135.83	151.74
Skew	1.17	1.22	1.11	0.16	1.01	1.71	1.32	1.65	0.24	1.18	0.74	1.32	1.26	0.71	0.75	1.73	1.60	1.45	2.01	1.99
Kurtosis	0.64	0.04	-0.04	-1.64	-0.84	2.39	0.42	2.24	-1.44	0.12	-0.82	-0.05	0.59	-0.27	-0.57	2.29	1.08	1.43	4.45	4.47

Figure 3: Shows trend of seasonal rainfall from 2015-2019

Table 2: Shows annual average temperature from the year 2015-2019													
Month wise temperature (°C)													
Year	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	June	July	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Avg.
2015	32.8	36.4	40.4	42.8	43.4	40.1	37.7	37.0	36.2	35	35.1	35.8	37.7
2016	35.8	40.1	41.6	44	43.2	39.7	34.4	34.0	33.6	31.6	34.1	33.6	37.1
2017	34.3	38.4	41.5	43.9	41.1	34.7	35.8	35.3	34.5	32.6	32.2	32.1	36.3
2018	33.6	37.6	41.1	43.9	44	36.9	35.6	35.3	35.3	37.0	35.8	34.0	37.5
2019	33.1	38.7	41.7	44.0	44.2	43.9	35.9	34.6	34.3	31.6	31.7	32.1	37.1
Max.	35.8	40.1	41.7	44.0	44.2	43.9	37.7	37.0	36.2	37.0	35.8	35.8	37.7
Min.	32.8	36.4	40.4	42.8	41.1	34.7	34.8	34.0	33.6	31.6	32.2	32.1	36.3
Mean	33.92	38.24	41.26	43.72	43.18	39.06	35.88	35.24	34.78	33.56	33.78	33.52	
SD	1.19	1.37	0.53	0.52	1.23	3.49	1.18	1.12	1.00	2.37	1.79	1.54	
CV %	3.52	3.58	1.29	1.18	2.86	8.92	3.29	3.19	2.87	7.07	5.28	4.59	
Skew	1.15	0.01	-1.39	-2.18	-1.64	0.21	0.70	0.96	0.51	0.87	-0.17	0.71	
Kurtosis	0.93	0.42	1.39	4.81	2.93	-0.10	2.10	1.50	-0.28	-1.11	-2.51	-0.14	

Trend analysis in various study shows that there are generally nonparametric (Hollander and Wolfe, 1973) methods were used, M-K test (Mann, 1945 Kendall, 1975) is one of the best methods among them, which is preferred by various researchers (Jain and Kumar, 2012). The descriptive statistics of rainfall such as the mean, SD, coefficient of variation, kurtosis and skewness are discussed in Table 1. And from the computed table, it has been found that the average monthly rainfall coefficient of variation (CV) ranging from 91.71 to 151.74 %. The highest values of coefficient of kurtosis was found for the month of December that is, 4.47 and also the skewness is found to be high for November that is, 2.01. Figure 2 explains the monthly

rainfall in all rain gauge stations pattern, which reveals that maximum amount of rainfall occur in monsoon months that is from June to September in the study area. Figure 3 is showing the general increasing trend of seasonal rainfall in the studied region, where the linear regression equation is showing positive slope value ($a = 1.274$) and the R^2 value comes about 0.254. R^2 which is coefficient of determination value explains that 36 % of variability in the seasonal rainfall is explained by this linear regression model. The recorded temperature data and the employed descriptive statistics like mean, SD, coefficient of variation, skewness and kurtosis are given in Table 2 and 3 for maximum and minimum temperature, respectively. Although the CV for both maximum and minimum temperature is found to be low as compared to rainfall but the skewness and kurtosis values show extreme variation than rainfall. The observed data were analyzed for the period of 2015–2019 and represented through the Figures 4 (a, b). From both of these figures, it become clear that the maximum and minimum temperature are low during monsoon seasons and are comparatively high during pre-monsoon months. Regarding temperature, trends found for both maximum and minimum temperature data on seasonal basis from 2015 to 2019 are not very significant. The maximum and minimum temperature trend analysis are presented in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. M-K test is also applied for trend test, result of which is shown in Table 3. The nonparametric test, M-K method, used to analyze if there is a monotonic upward or downward trend of the variable over time, the result (Table 3) shows that there is a trend in the seasonal rainfall pattern over the studied districts. Statistically significant trends are detected for rainfall and also the result is statistically significant at 95 % confident level during the period of 2015–2019 and here, it is noteworthy to mention that the 95 % confident level has been decided on the basis of “z” score value. Rainfall is showing a quite good increasing trend (Sen's slope = 2.013) during monsoon season. In general, maximum temperature for the observed period showed a slight warming or increasing trend (Sen's slope = 0.18) while the minimum temperature trend showed a cooling trend (Sen's slope = -0.004) but result of maximum temperature trend analysis is statistically significant at 95 % confidence limit, on the contrary the trend analysis result of minimum temperature is not statistically significant.

Table 3: Shows Mann-Kendall trend analysis

Non-parametric test	Seasonal rainfall	Max. Temp (°C)	Min. Temp. (°C)
Kendal tau	0.342	0.243	-0.055
Sen's slope	2.013	0.21	-0.055
S	208	154	-33
P-value	0.001	0.025	0.252
Significance	Significant	Significant	Not significant

(a)

(b)

Figure 4 (a,b): Shows max. and min. Temperature from 2015-2019**DISCUSSION:**

A variability analysis of meteorological parameters is crucial for researchers and policymakers in their decision-making, as rainfall plays a dominant role in determining water availability in various regions. At first glance, monthly rainfall variations have been illustrated using box and whisker plots. The compact nature of box and whisker plots (Tukey, 1977) facilitates side-by-

side assessments of multiple datasets, which can otherwise be challenging to interpret using more detailed representations, such as histograms. (Banacos, 2011). These plots visually represent the statistical distribution in a manner that is easily comprehensible for a broad audience. The form of the box and whisker plot here includes: a central horizontal line representing the median and the top and bottom horizontal lines of the interquartile range. (Shown by the box). The bottom and top horizontal lines in the boxes represent the 25th and 75th percentiles, respectively. The outer ranges are depicted as vertical lines. (As shown by the whiskers). The position of the median line can indicate skewness in the distribution if it is significantly displaced from the center. The length of the interquartile range, as indicated by the box, measures the relative dispersion of the middle 50% of a dataset, just as the length of each whisker measures the relative dispersion of the dataset's outer range (10th to 25th percentiles and 75th to 90th percentiles). (Banacos, 2011). Therefore, it is clearly observe that the datasets are not normally disseminated, and most of the data fall in the upper whisker, that is, in the 4th quartile. According to the IMD standards, the coefficient of variation (CV) is used to classify the degree of variability as low ($CV < 20\%$), moderate ($20 < CV < 30\%$), high ($CV > 30\%$), very high ($CV > 40\%$), and $CV > 70\%$ indicates extremely high inter-annual variability of rainfall. Based on this, the observed data indicated that all months had a coefficient of variation (CV) above 30%, highlighting the high variability of precipitation in the area. The result indicated that the amount of rainfall in the region is highly variable. Then, if the kurtosis values are analyzed, it can be understood that during the monsoon, the kurtosis values are lower, and the skewness value indicates that the dataset is light-tailed during the monsoon months and follows a symmetric pattern. In other words, we can say that rainfall in the study area exhibits a symmetric pattern during the monsoon months. In contrast, during the post-monsoon and pre-monsoon months, the dataset shows a high kurtosis value, indicating that rainfall during these periods has a heavy-tailed nature, which means there are outliers or extreme values present. In its simplest form, it can be stated that rainfall in the study area before and after the monsoon months is asymmetrical in nature. Surface air temperature is one of the most crucial elements in weather and climate forecasting, so examining its behavior is essential for understanding climate variability, which can differ spatially and temporally across various local, regional, and global scales. (Ghasemi, 2015). Despite the overwhelming evidence of rising temperatures worldwide, accurately estimating the time trends remains an unresolved issue. (Gil-Alana, 2018). In a similar way to

how air temperature has a crucial impact on the water cycle in the study area, a deep understanding of the nature of its occurrence must be pursued. Unlike rainfall, the seasonal maximum and minimum temperatures exhibit a decreasing trend as rainfall reaches its peak during these months in the study area. And before and after the monsoon months, the temperature shows an increasing trend. Figure 4 (a) shows the seasonal mean maximum temperature and its trend during the period under analysis. Using a linear regression model, the rate of change is defined by the slope of the regression line, which in this case is approximately $0.0021\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ per 5 years during the period from 2015 to 2019. This finding is not comparable to the global warming rate, which is estimated to be $0.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the last decade. This result indicates that the approach to studying global warming has had a significant impact on the regional climate in the study area over the past two decades. It is also observed that the average monthly maximum temperature for the studied period has a coefficient of variation (CV) ranging from 1.29 to 7.07%. This indicates that, more or less, the maximum temperature demonstrates stability over time and exhibits less variability. The coefficient of kurtosis for maximum temperature is highest in April, at 4.81, and the data is positively skewed. The trends of seasonal mean minimum temperature over different years are also obtained using linear regression best-fit lines. The linear regression trends along with their linear regression equations and coefficients of determination are shown in Figure 4 (b).

CONCLUSION:

Climate variability in the Afzalpur taluk is a significant issue, impacting social and economic interactions. Rainfall and temperature are the most decisive climatic factors, as over 80 % of agriculture depends on rain. The study analyzed meteorological data using the nonparametric Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope estimator. The results indicated that the highest rainfall occurred during the monsoon months, while the variability in maximum and minimum temperatures remained stable throughout all months. This suggests that underdeveloped areas like Afzalpur taluk are highly vulnerable to climate variability, especially rainfall, which is essential for agricultural development. Therefore, stakeholders should take into account the variability of rainfall and temperature in their climate change adaptation strategies.

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